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Impact of fertiliser use reduction

The case of the European Union

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DELIVERABLE LEADER:	Ana Gonzalez-Martinez
AUTHOR:	Ana Gonzalez-Martinez, Sonja G. Keel
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Abstract

This study provides some insights regarding the potential impacts of reducing nitrogen (N) fertilisation by 20 % in the case of selected crops: wheat, rapeseed, sugar beet, maize and barley. In terms of the geographical scope, this report provides insights for the EU27 and the UK, generated by means of the AGMEMOD model. In general terms, the decline in fertiliser use could induce a decline in yields (unless overfertilisation occurs currently), while the related decline in production could lead to an increase in the prices of the relevant crops. In addition, the reduction in fertiliser application is likely to affect the quality of agricultural production, leading to lower prices at farm-gate level. The net price effect will depend on the size and direction of these opposing impacts, i.e. price increase due to scarcity versus price decline due to quality deterioration.

As shown in the scenario simulation, the achievement of the intended 20 % reduction in N fertilisation is expected to result in lower productivity (yields), and subsequently, lower production volumes. Lower supplied volumes affect exports patterns, as well as food self-sufficiency rates. According to the simulation the strongest declines in self-sufficiency rates are projected in the case of rapeseed and barley.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

AGMEMOD	<i>AGricultural MEmber State MODelling</i>
EU	<i>European Union</i>
F2F	<i>Farm-to-Fork Strategy</i>
GAMS	<i>General algebraic modeling system</i>
MITERRA	<i>MITERRA-Europe</i>
SIMPLE	<i>Scenario modelling for assessing impacts of policy changes and socio-economic effects on ecosystem services of soils</i>
SOC	<i>Soil Organic Carbon</i>
SUPREMA	<i>Support for Policy Relevant Modelling of Agriculture</i>
UK	<i>United Kingdom</i>
WP	<i>Work Package</i>

1. Introduction

1.1. Overview

In the course of 2021, several studies investigated the potential impacts of implementing the Farm-to-Fork strategy on productivity, affecting eventually the total volume of agricultural production (Beckman et al. 2021; Bremmer et al. 2021; Jongeneel et al. 2021).¹ These studies show that the implementation of all suggested measures which are part of the Farm-to-Fork and the Biodiversity Strategy (i.e., reduction of pesticides, fertiliser, antimicrobials, and agricultural land), could indeed lead to a 12% reduction in total agricultural production. However, how this reduction would affect soil quality, including the capacity of soils for agricultural production and their role for climate mitigation is not clear yet. It is therefore urgently necessary to assess the impact of policy scenarios that affect agricultural fertilisation regimes on ecosystem services such as potential yield and yield stability, GHG balances and potential Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) reductions at the European scale. It is critical to understand where or under which conditions soils are likely to lose or gain capacity for ecosystem services if fertilisation rates are reduced. All these questions have been investigated in the context of the SIMPLE (Scenario modelling for assessing impacts of policy changes and socio-economic effects on ecosystem services of soils) project.

This deliverable presents the main outcomes of Task 2.1, carried out as part of WP2: Socio-economic scenarios. The overall objective of WP2 is to assess the magnitude of the potential impacts of policy changes and socio-economic effects related to changes on fertilisation rates. More specifically, this deliverable contributes to the following specific objective:

- OB2.1: To estimate the impact of Farm-to-Fork fertiliser use reduction: Using the AGMEMOD model the project team will estimate the effects of applying lower fertiliser rates as proposed in the Farm to Fork strategy.

Regarding the methodology, this deliverable presents the outcomes of a scenario simulated by means of the AGMEMOD model (see, Section 1.2 for further details). In terms of the geographical coverage, indicators for the EU27 ('EU' hereinafter) and the United Kingdom (UK) are delivered. The simulated impacts reported in this document covered elements such as land use, production, prices, net trade and self-sufficiency rates among others.

The reader should be aware that this study does not intend to be a comprehensive assessment which considers all sorts of farming activities. Instead, this study only focuses on selected crops: wheat, rapeseed, sugar beet, maize and barley.

1.2. Method: The AGMEMOD model

AGMEMOD stands for 'AGricultural MEMber states MODelling' (<https://agmemod.eu/>). Since 2001, it has been developed by the AGMEMOD Partnership, a consortium of national university institutes and research agencies from EU countries and potential accession countries (Chantreuil et al., 2011). It is a dynamic, partial, multi-country, multi-market equilibrium system which solves in a GAMS environment (Leeuwen et al., 2008). It can provide significant detail on the main agricultural sectors in each EU Member State, with most equations being estimated econometrically at the individual Member State level. Where estimation was not feasible or meaningful, parameters have been calibrated. The country models contain the behavioral responses of economic agents (farmers, consumers) to changes in

¹ The reader is also referred to Barreiro Hurlé et al. (2021) for an assessment of the Farm-to-Fork and Biodiversity strategies targets by means of the CAPRI model.

prices, policy instruments and other exogenous variables on the agricultural market. Within AGMEMOD, all commodity prices clear all markets under consideration, i.e. supply and demand are equal.

The current AGMEMOD version consists of the EU28 Member States, the Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, Turkey, Russia and Ukraine (AGMEMOD Consortium; 2010, 2011). Moreover, some attempts of introducing a regional disaggregation have been done in the case of Germany and Ukraine. A bottom-up approach has been used to integrate country models into AGMEMOD. For each commodity in each country, agricultural production as well as supply, demand, trade, stocks and domestic prices are derived from econometrically estimated equations. One element of the supply and demand balance for each commodity is used as a closure variable to make the balance consistent. For a closer representation of market dynamics, the specification of the equations that are used for a given commodity can differ across countries. AGMEMOD’s projections offer an interesting combination of econometric results and expert knowledge. In other words, the modelling systems' projections are validated by standard econometric methods and through consultation with experts who are familiar with the agricultural market in the regions under study. The AGMEMOD model provides output for the following agricultural commodities: (i) cereals (soft wheat, durum wheat, barley, maize, rye, other grains); (ii) oilseeds (rapeseed, sunflower seed, soybeans, cotton seeds, vegetables oils and meals); (iii) livestock and meat (beef and veal, pork, poultry, sheep and goats); (iv) milk and dairy products (butter, skimmed milk powder and cheese); (v) fruits and vegetables sector (tomatoes, oranges, apples, olive oil); (vi) industrial crops (sugar beets tobacco and cotton) and potatoes; and (vii) bioethanol (from grains) and biodiesel (from oilseeds).

In the context of Bremmer et al. (2021), the AGMEMOD model was used to assess the impact of the Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategies. This study provides an ex-ante assessment of the potential effects of both Strategies at sectoral, national and EU level, with the AGMEMOD model delivering indicators at national and EU level.

1.3. Further contribution of Task 2.1

Figure 1 provides an overview of how the activities carried out in the context of Task 2.1 relates to other work packages (WPs). It also provides an illustration of how two of the modelling tools involved in the SIMPLE project are interacting to deliver a comprehensive set of simulation results.

Figure 1. Model linkages and interaction between WPs. In SIMPLE not all indicators of MITERRA-Europe were included (see main text). Source: SIMPLE.

Before commenting on the scenarios, a clarification is due regarding Figure 1. The reader should be aware that the blue box in the figure lists a selection of key indicators that could be compiled by combining AGMEMOD-MITERRA. However, some of the indicators included in the diagram fall beyond the scope of the project, e.g. NH₃, CH₄, etc. They are only included here to inform the reader about the potential contribution of the two models when working together.

Coming back to WP2, the scenario shocks whose impact have been investigated in Task 2.1 relies on the yield shocks that were calculated in the context of WP3: Yields. Subsequently, those changes in production (reflecting changes in yields as calculated in WP3) could be used as input for the MITERRA-Europe model (Velthof et al., 2009; Lesschen et al., 2011) to compute the relevant environmental indicators (WP5: Greenhouse gas emissions and N losses).

The combination AGMEMOD-MITERRA has been applied before in the H2020 SUPREMA (Support for Policy Relevant Modelling of Agriculture) project to assess changes in diets and the expansion of biodiversity favourable land in the EU (Jongeneel et al., 2020).²

1.4. Structure

After this introduction the layout of the report is as follows. To begin with, the storyline of the simulated scenario is presented in Section 2.1. Subsequently, the results of the simulation carried out by means of the AGMEMOD model are presented in Section 2.2. Then, some conclusions and remarks regarding future research are provided in Chapter 3. Finally, a list of references is presented to close the report.

² See: https://www.suprema-project.eu/images/Deliverable_D32.pdf.

2. Case of the EU

2.1.Scenario narrative

In the context of WP3, information on fertilisation recommendations has been gathered. Subsequently, based on equations derived from long-term field trials (Hijbeek et al; Van Grinsven et al.) the research team has estimated the expected yields assuming a 20% reduction in mineral N fertilization. The final set of yields calculated as indicated above has been used to compute the relevant yield reductions used as exogenous shocks for the AGMEMOD simulation (Table 1).

Table 1. Expected yield reductions (%)

	Wheat	Rapeseed	Sugar beet	Maize	Barley	Potato
AT	10.1	20.0	9.4	8.6	11.4	10.2
BE+LUX	9.6	20.9	8.1	4.7	9.4	6.0
BG	10.9	20.9	9.7	4.7	10.4	4.7
CY	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
CZ	11.2	19.8	10.9	11.4	11.1	10.8
DK	5.4	18.1	7.0	4.7	10.5	7.2
DE	5.4	20.4	10.5	10.4	11.4	8.6
EE	11.1	17.0	4.7	9.7	11.2	11.2
ES	11.0	18.1	8.3	4.5	9.1	10.6
FI	11.4	20.9	10.4	8.1	10.8	9.8
FR	8.4	20.9	6.5	8.1	10.5	9.7
GR	8.1	18.1	8.3	8.1	9.1	9.3
HU	9.9	17.0	4.7	9.7	11.1	7.5
HR	9.8	18.1	9.8	11.4	9.0	7.8
IE	6.9	18.1	8.1	10.2	10.2	4.7
IT	8.1	18.1	10.8	8.1	9.1	9.3
LV	11.1	20.9	10.7	10.3	11.4	7.9
LT	11.0	17.0	4.7	9.7	11.2	11.2
MT	8.1	18.1	10.8	8.1	9.1	9.3
NL	6.3	20.9	11.2	10.1	10.7	6.1
PL	11.0	20.9	11.2	10.4	11.4	11.4
PT	10.4	18.1	8.3	1.8	10.4	9.3
RO	9.8	20.4	8.5	9.8	9.0	8.6
SK	11.2	20.2	6.5	4.7	9.9	7.8
SI	9.9	20.0	11.4	10.4	9.4	9.3
SE	7.9	19.7	11.4	11.4	11.4	11.2
UK	6.9	20.9	10.3	10.2	11.1	9.1

Source: SIMPLE project, WP3, Madenoglu et al. 2024.

Note: In the AGMEMOD model, Belgium and Luxembourg are modelled as a single entity.

When implementing the exogenous yield reductions presented below in the AGMEMOD model, the mentioned yield declines are linearly distributed over the period 2021-2030.

Although WP3 has delivered estimated reductions in the case of potatoes, these impacts are not included in the present simulation since this crop is not a key commodity in the AGMEMOD model. Nevertheless, the shocks are included in Table 1 only for informative purposes.

2.2. Results

In general terms, the decline in fertiliser use could induce a decline in yields (unless overfertilisation occurs), while the related decline in production could lead to an increase in the prices of the relevant crops. In addition, the reduction in fertiliser application is likely to affect the quality of agricultural production, leading to lower prices at farm-gate level. The net price effect will depend on the size and direction of these opposing impacts, i.e. price increase due to scarcity *versus* price decline due to quality deterioration (see, also Bremmer et al., 2021).

The remaining part of this section presents key indicators of the simulation. For an easier interpretation of the results, the reference and fertiliser reduction scenarios are compared and only the differences between both scenarios in 2030 are included. The results are provided for the EU27 and the UK.

Land use

Table 2 reports on the simulated changes in cultivated areas that could result from reaching the fertiliser reduction target. This reflects changes in profitability for the various crops, with the underlying factor being prices changes in response to available supply. In the case of EU27, cultivated areas for rapeseed and barley could decline almost by 3% compared with baseline levels. On the contrary, an expansion of sugar beet acreage could be expected in both the EU27 and the UK (9% and 10% respectively).

Table 2. Acreage in the EU27 and UK (% deviation from baseline in 2030)

	EU27	UK
Wheat	-0.2	1.2
Rapeseed	-2.7	-4.0
Sugar beet	9.0	10.4
Maize	0.1	0.5
Barley	-2.6	-0.5

Source: AGMEMOD.

Production

Table 3 presents the impacts on production related to the achievement of the intended fertiliser use reduction, reported as differences between the scenario and the baseline values in 2030.³ As shown in the table, the strongest production declines are expected in the case of rapeseed (22% and 24% for the EU and the UK respectively). In contrast, production changes in the case of sugar beet are marginal. This is so since the expansion in acreage compensates the decline in yields, resulting in almost stable production compared to the 2030 baseline level.

³ The reader is referred to Bremmer et al. (2021). See, Figure 2.3, for a description of the scenario mechanism.

Table 3. Production at EU27 and UK level (% deviation from baseline in 2030)

	EU27	UK
Wheat	-8.4	-5.8
Rapeseed	-22.1	-24.0
Sugar beet	-0.6	-0.8
Maize	-8.0	0.0
Barley	-13.0	-11.6

Source: AGMEMOD.

Consumption

Moving onto consumption impacts, Table 4 reports the relevant changes in the case of apparent consumption in per capita levels. As shown in the table, differences for wheat, maize and barley are marginal which reflects a relatively inelastic demand.

Table 4. Per capita (apparent) consumption at EU27 and UK level (% deviation from baseline in 2030)

	EU27	UK
Wheat	-0.2	-0.1
Rapeseed	---	---
Sugar beet	---	---
Maize	-0.1	0.0
Barley	0.0	0.0

Source: AGMEMOD. NB. --- means 'Not available'.

Prices

Table 5 presents the relevant price impacts, reflecting supply and demand market dynamics. For the EU, the largest price increases are expected in the case of rapeseed (around 13%), while price impacts are much lower in the case sugar beet and barley (2.7% and 1.2% respectively). In the UK case, prices for sugar beet and wheat could increase by almost 5%, while price increases of around 10% could be expected in the case of rapeseed.

Table 5. Prices at EU27 and UK level (% deviation from baseline in 2030)

	EU27	UK
Wheat	4.1	4.7
Rapeseed	12.7	10.3
Sugar beet	2.7	4.7
Maize	3.4	2.8
Barley	1.2	0.4

Source: AGMEMOD.

Net trade

Bringing together the supply and demand sides of the agricultural market, Table 6 reports on the changes in net trade that could emanate from achieving the 20% reduction in fertiliser use. To correctly interpret the results, a reference to the net trade position of the EU and the UK is needed. More specifically, the EU is a net importer of maize, rapeseed and sugar beet, while it is a net exporter of wheat and barley. The UK is a net exporter of barley and rapeseed, being a net importer of all the other commodities under consideration. As shown in the table, EU net exports of wheat are expected to decline by more than 30%. Imports strongly increase in the EU for rapeseed and maize (116% and 112% respectively). In the case of both regions, net exports of barley could substantially decline, with reductions by at least 50%.

Table 6. Net trade at EU27 and UK level (% deviation from baseline in 2030)

	EU27	UK
Wheat	-32.4	135.2
Rapeseed	116.3	-184.0
Sugar beet	0.0	0.0
Maize	111.9	0.0
Barley	-54.7	-61.0

Source: AGMEMOD.

Food self-sufficiency

Table 7 presents the expected changes in the case of food self-sufficiency rates in both regions. According to the simulation the EU is expected to remain self-sufficient in the case of wheat and barley, although at a lower level. A similar development could occur in the UK in the case of barley. Moreover, the simulation also suggests that in the UK the expected decline in rapeseed production (-24% compared to the 2030 baseline level) could result into a strong decline in the self-sufficiency rate, with the country becoming a net importer.

Table 7. Self-sufficiency rates in EU27 and the UK (% deviation from baseline in 2030)

	EU27	UK
Wheat	-7.8	-5.3
Rapeseed	-17.6	-23.9
Sugar beet	0.0	0.0
Maize	-7.3	0.0
Barley	-13.2	-9.8

Source: AGMEMOD.

3. Conclusion

3.1. Concluding remarks

This study provides some insights regarding the potential impacts of reducing mineral N fertilisation by 20 % in the case of selected crops: wheat, rapeseed, sugar beet, maize and barley. In terms of the geographical scope, this report provides insights for the EU and the UK, generated by means of the AGMEMOD model. As shown in the scenario simulation, the achievement of the intended 20 % reduction in N fertilisation could result in lower productivity (yields), and subsequently, lower production volumes. Lower supplied volumes affect export patterns, as well as food self-sufficiency rates. According to the simulation the strongest declines in self-sufficiency rates are projected in the case of rapeseed and barley.

Similarly, as in the case of Bremmer et al. (2021), the outcomes of this study have limitations, mainly related to the fact that the focus is on crop production, leaving out the potential impacts that both the Farm-to-Fork and Biodiversity strategies have on livestock production as well as consumer behavior (dietary patterns and food waste reductions). As a consequence, our results may overestimate the trade impacts. Moreover, another important aspect is that the AGMEMOD model has an EU focus. Its EU scope makes the model less suitable for simulating world price impacts endogenously. This could lead to some underestimation of the price responses in our case relative to those obtained in other studies (Beckman et al., 2021; Barreiro Hurlé et al., 2021).⁴ Apart from that, in this study, we do not simulate changes in farmers's behavior like replacing the studied crops with N fixing crops that do not require N fertilisation (such as soyabean).

A final remark in terms of the interpretation and further use of the modelling outcomes presented in this study is due. This scenario has only illustrative purposes and should be considered as hypothetical. A comprehensive assessment of the implications of the Farm-to-Fork and Biodiversity strategies would require a much more complex modelling exercise in which exogenous shocks on a broader set of activities, e.g. other crops and livestock farming, together with additional policy measures and further price dynamics, e.g. reflecting quality deterioration and/or scarcity due to lower production, should be also included. Nevertheless, the results of this study are still insightful since they can help us to understand the potential implications of lower productivity in the agricultural sector. These remarks are still informative for policymakers when developing policies to ensure/foster economic and environmental sustainability of farming activities.

3.2. Future research

The Farm-to-Fork Strategy is an ambitious policy whose complex impact still deserves further investigation given the heterogeneity of agricultural production and farming systems across the EU. Thinking of future research, the work presented in this report could be extended in follow-up analysis. More specifically, alternative scenarios to explore the potential impacts of reducing mineral fertilisation could be simulated, for example, by extending the type of crops included in the analysis or by carrying out sensitivity analysis in which shocks on yields of a different magnitude are investigated. Another possibility could be also to simulate scenarios in which impacts of yields due to reduced

⁴ The scenario assumptions (and how individual cases/experiments have been aggregated into sectoral/macro shocks) could add additional uncertainty to the interpretation of the scenario outcomes. These assumptions could be further refined if additional information becomes available. Since the exogenous shocks on yields have been 'inherited' from the WP3, the reader is referred to the relevant deliverables produced in this WP.

fertilisation are combined with shocks on prices, reflecting the changes in quality due to different strategies of pest management.

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